

Figure S1. NMDS ordination plots showing clustering of samples by time point. Columns correspond to dataset type; 16S, ITS, and Metabolomics are columns one, two, and three, respectively (n=294, 319, and 144).

Figure S2. Correlation matrices between comparisons of different datasets (bacteria-fungi, bacteria-metabolites, and fungi-metabolites) on wet materials. (A) Bacterial-fungal correlations on gypsum; (B) Bacterial-fungal correlations on mold-free gypsum; (C) Bacterial-fungal correlations on plywood; (D) Bacteria-metabolite correlations on gypsum; (E) Bacteria-metabolite correlations on mold-free gypsum; (F) Bacteria-metabolite correlations on plywood; (G) Fungai-metabolite correlations on gypsum; (H) Fungi-metabolite correlations on mold-free gypsum; (I) Fungi-metabolite correlations on plywood; (J) Fungi-metabolite correlations on MDF; All spaces with color are $p\text{-adj} < 0.05$. Red indicates a positive correlation, blue a negative correlation.

A Bacteria-Fungal Correlations on Wet Gypsum

B

Bacteria-Fungal Correlations on Wet Mold-Free Gypsum

C

Bacteria-Fungal Correlations on Wet Plywood

E

Bacteria-Metabolite Correlations on Wet Mold-free Gypsum

G

Fungi-Metabolite Correlations on Wet Gypsum

H

Fungi-Metabolite Correlations on Wet Mold-Free Gypsum

I

Fungi-Metabolite Correlations on Wet Plywood

